

Hanbalism

also known as “Hanbali”, “Hanbalites”, “Hanabila”

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Hanbalism is one of the four Sunni schools of Muslim law, and adherents to this school are often known as the Hanabila, Hanbalites, or Hanbalis. Hanbalis are Muslim legal scholars or theologians who base their views about God and humankind on the teachings of Ahmad ibn Hanbal (d. 855 CE). Ibn Hanbal is said to have memorized tens of thousands of reports attributed to the Prophet Muhammad, called hadith. These reports, along with the texts embodying the practice of Muhammad's companions, called Sunnah, are the sources for moral, social, and devotional life. Hanbalis reject any rational, speculative interpretation of God's will through the Quran and the Sunnah. They interpret God's will and nature through rigid literal interpretation, and believe that God's will can be known with certainty. Hanbalis won over the hearts and minds of scholars and common people alike in early periods of their formation, resulting in a social and political movement. Some Hanbalis served in high government posts and judgeships, even at times of contention with ruling authorities. The movement began and thrived in Baghdad, Iraq for well over five centuries, with some spells of adversity by Shi'i rulers, and a movement of some Hanbalis to Palestine and Syria, where the movement enjoyed two centuries of flourishing. Their popularity in the premodern period reached a pinnacle during the fourteenth century, a time when the school thrived as a result of the works of Ibn Taymiyya. Though Hanbalism is a legal school that trains scholars, non-scholars may consider themselves adherents to the teachings of the legal school by subscribing to the teaching of the school or implementing them in their own lives, such as for devotion and worship. The legacy of Hanbalism in the premodern period continues through the modern period, when the movement was adopted in part by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Date Range: 850 CE - 1350 CE

Region: Western Asia

Region tags: Syria, Iran, Turkey, Iraq

Places of consistent Hanbali presence or political appointments

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cook, Michael. *Commanding Right and Forbidding Wrong*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- Source 2: Melchert, Christopher. *The Formation of the Sunni Schools of Law, 9th-10th centuries C.E.* Leiden: Brill, 1997.
- Source 3: Hurvitz, Nimrod. *The Formation of Hanbalism: Piety Into Power*. New York: Routledge, 2002.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_ei3_COM_23414
- Source 1 Description: Encyclopedia of Islam 3, "Ahmad b. Hanbal"
- Source 2 URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_0263
- Source 2 Description: Encyclopedia of Islam 2, "Hanabila"

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.libraryofarabicliterature.org/assets/Cooperson-Virtues-of-the-Imam-Ahmad-ibn-Hanbal-Arabic-only-1-modified-2.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Source Text, Biography of Ibn Hanbal, "Virtues of the Imam Ahmad ibn Hanbal," volume 1. Arabic.
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.libraryofarabicliterature.org/assets/Cooperson-Virtues-of-the-Imam-Ahmad-ibn-Hanbal-Arabic-only-1-modified-2.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: Source Text, Biography of Ibn Hanbal, "Virtues of the Imam Ahmad ibn Hanbal," volume 2. Arabic.
- Source 3 URL: <https://shamela.ws/category/17>
- Source 3 Description: Database and Application: Hanbali legal works

Notes: There are many more sources for the Hanbali school of law that can be found in the Shamela database (Source 3).

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Muslims were generally in contact with other religious groups, such as Christians and Jews.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Assigned by education in a school or by volunteer affiliation

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic states in which Muslims subscribing to Hanbali positions took different positions against scholars and jurists of this legal school. In the early period of the school's formation, for example, Hanbalism was condemned by the Abbasid Caliph al-Radi (d. 940 CE) due to some

members religious zeal. Again Hanbalism was also an object of ridicule in Iraq and Egypt under Shi'i rule. At the same time, however, the Sunni Caliph of Baghdad al-Qa'im (d. 1075 CE), now a figurehead, employed the Hanbali scholar Abu Ya'la b. al-Farra (d. 1055) during Shi'i Buyid rule, resulting in a period of rich legal and scholarly production. But the Buyids apparently only recognized the Sunni Caliph for legitimacy, which translated to tacit approval and political support at best. Hanbalism received political support during a period of the revival of Sunnism and the appearance of new Muslim dynasties of the Ayyubids and the Zangids in Syria. Hanbalism flourished for two centuries in Iraq (Baghdad), Syria, and Palestine, with tentative political support of different rulers.

Reference: H Laoust undefined Hanabila

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Apostasy is comprehensively treated in the works of jurisprudence and fiqh (understanding). A Muslim who renounces his faith through conversion to another community of faith or by a denial of the shahada, a testimony about the prophethood of Muhammad and the oneness of God, is an apostate. Any Muslim claiming to be a prophet would also be considered an apostate, as it would invalidate the finality of the revelation given to Muhammad, the final prophet.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: An apostate is typically given a chance to repent, in accordance with Quran 8: 38. If the apostate refuses, they are subject to execution. The Hanbalis take different positions, some offering repentance and others not. For Ibn Hanbal, an apostate might be given a chance to repent, but that it is also justifiable to kill them before offering a chance.

Reference: Yohanan Friedmann. *Tolerance and Coercion in Islam: Interfaith Relations in the Muslim Tradition*. Cambridge. isbn: 978-0-521-82703.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– I don't know

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are executed:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are publicly executed:

– Yes

- ↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
 - Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

- I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

- I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

- Yes

↳ Are they written:

- Yes

Notes: The Quran is the foundation of lawmaking, as are the Hadith and Sunnah. The Hadith are oral reports about the Prophet Muhammad's words and deeds which were written down or memorized by Ibn Hanbal. The Sunnah are reports about Muhammad and his early followers as written down or remembered and transmitted orally through the earliest generation of trustworthy Muslims.

↳ Are they oral:

- Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

- Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

- Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Interpretation of Shariah takes place in other legal schools. But these are not always in agreement with the Hanabli interpretation.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: There is a select group of jurists who are trained in transmitting the sources of knowledge about God, such as the Hadith and Sunnah.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: There are a variety of sources that can be drawn upon, but this is not a fixed canon, since one jurist may draw upon a source of law that another jurist may not.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for all

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes

Notes: The Quran describes God as having human traits. Since the Hanbalis accept a literal interpretation of the Quran and Sunnah, they are unable to avoid interpreting God anthropomorphically. In the Quran, for example, God has hands and a face. But most Hanbalis would reject the label of anthropomorphist, preferring to call themselves "those who affirm" God's attributes. Hanbalis developed doctrines on the attributes of God that distanced them from attributing to God human likeness. Some interpreted the sources figuratively, and others left the issue as unexplainable or unnecessary to explain. The issue of anthropomorphism also caused intra-communal disputes, such as Ibn al-Jawzi (d. 1201 CE), a famous Hanbali theologian, accusing the legal scholar Abu Ya'la b. al-Farra (d. 1066) of holding anthropomorphist views over a century after the latter's death.

Reference: Livnat Holtzman. Anthropomorphism in Islam. Edinburgh University Press. isbn: 978 0 7486 8956 9.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Merciful and compassionate, Forgiving and Hearing

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Based on a hadith of Ibn Abbas that says, "God knows what they would have done [had they lived]."

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God is omnipotent and all-powerful. He knows all.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what

you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

- ↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Day of Judgment, unspecified

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– I don't know

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– I don't know

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No

- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Charity

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Caliphate

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Charity tax, but it is optional

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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